

Viscosity Variation with Composition : An Explanation in Terms of Various Solution Parameters

(Miss) KRISHNA ROY CHOUDHURY and DILIP K. MAJUMDAR

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal

Manuscript received 15 March 1980, revised 6 September 1980, accepted 9 September, 1980

The relative viscosities of naphthalene, durenene, fluoranthene, fluorene, 2:3-dimethylnaphthalene, 2:6-dimethylnaphthalene and hexamethylbenzene have been measured in several solvents, namely toluene, *o*-xylene, *p*-xylene, *m*-xylene, mesitylene and heptane in the low concentration range of the solutes at 35°. It is noticed that the viscosity function, F decreases in the same order as the experimental slope, $S_o = d\eta_{rel}/dX_s$.

NUMEROUS attempts¹ have been made over several decades to arrive at a correct formulation for the variation of viscosity of liquid mixtures as a function of composition. These attempts have been only partially successful. In the case of electrolyte solutions, however, Jones-Dole equation² has gained wide acceptance, especially because the parameters in the Jones-Dole equation are useful in obtaining an idea about ion-ion and ion-solvent interaction. Unfortunately it has not proved successful till now to interpret variation of viscosity of non-electrolyte liquid mixtures in a similar fashion and enable us to get information about solute-solute or solute-solvent interaction.

In the present article, we shall endeavour to show that the viscosity equation for liquid mixtures, proposed by Irving and Smith^{3,4} provides us with an interpretation of viscosity variation in terms of solution parameters. Irving and Smith³ extended Eyring theory of viscosity⁵ to regular solutions and wrote for the relative viscosity, η_{rel} the following expression,

$$\eta_{rel} = \frac{\eta_g}{\eta} = \frac{V_1^0}{V_g} \exp [(\Delta E_g^* - \Delta E_1^*)/ART] \quad \dots (1)$$

In equation (1) η_g is the absolute viscosity of the solution, η is the viscosity of the pure solvent, ΔE_g^* and ΔE_1^* are the molar energies of vaporisation of the solution and of the solvent respectively; V_g and V_1^0 are the molar volumes respectively of the solution and of the pure solvent, and A is a constant whose value is approximately 2.5. Now the energy of vaporisation of the solution, ΔE_g^* is related to the energy change ΔE^M on mixing by the relation,

$$\Delta E_g^* = X_1 \Delta E_1^* + X_2 \Delta E_2^* - \Delta E^M \quad \dots (2)$$

at mole fraction X_1 and X_2 in respect of solvent and solute respectively. ΔE_1^* and ΔE_2^* are the molar energy of vaporisation of solvent and solute

respectively. Following Scatchard⁶, Irving and Smith³ employed

$$\Delta E^M = (\delta_1 - \delta_2)^2 X_2 \bar{V}_2$$

in very dilute solutions; δ_1 and δ_2 are the solubility parameters⁷ of solvent and solute and \bar{V}_2 is the partial molal volume of the solute. Noting that in very dilute solutions $V_1^0/V_g \approx 1$, Irving and Smith³ finally obtained

$$\eta_{rel} = 1 + S_o X_s \quad \dots (3)$$

In equation (3) S_o represents the rate of variation of η_{rel} with mole fraction of the solute, $d\eta_{rel}/dX_s$ and is given by

$$S_o = \{-\delta_1^2(V_1^0 + \bar{V}_2) + 2\bar{V}_2\delta_1\delta_2\}/ART \quad \dots (4)$$

for solutions having $\bar{V}_1 \approx V_1^0$.

Let us now study the consequences flowing from Irving and Smith equation (3). We define the viscosity function, F as follows :

$$F = \bar{V}_2 \left(\frac{2\delta_2}{\delta_1} - 1 \right) \quad \dots (5)$$

With the aid of the viscosity function, F we can rewrite expression (4) for S_o ,

$$S_o = \{\delta_1^2(F - V_1^0)\}/ART \quad \dots (6)$$

It follows that the value of S_o will be positive only if F is positive (i.e. $2\delta_2 > \delta_1$) and greater than V_1^0 .

It is seen that the solubility parameters together with the partial molar volumes of solvent and solute determine the variation of viscosity with composition. That this is borne out by experimental results is described below with reference to viscosity of solutions of solutes. ortho-terphenyl, 2,3-dimethylnaphthalene, 2,6-dimethylnaphthalene, fluoranthene,

fluorene, hexamethylbenzene, naphthalene and durene in several solvents, namely, toluene, xylenes, mesitylene and *n*-heptane.

Experimental

Materials : The solvents used are : mesitylene (Merck, Germany), *n*-heptane (BDH, England), *o*-xylene (BDH, England) *p*- and *m*-xylene (E. Merck, Germany), toluene (International Chemical Industry, Calcutta). *n*-Heptane was fractionally distilled. Toluene was purified by shaking several times with concentrated H_2SO_4 . It was then shaken first with water, then sodium carbonate solution and again with water and finally dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and fractionally distilled. All the solvents were freshly distilled before use. Naphthalene (E. M., Germany), Durene (KL, England), 2 : 3-dimethylnaphthalene (KL, England), 2 : 6-dimethylnaphthalene (KL, England), *o*-terphenyl (KL, England), fluoranthene (KL, England), fluorene (KL, England) were the best quality available and recrystallised from appropriate solvents.

Measurement of density and viscosity :

The densities of the pure solvents and of solutions were measured by a bicapillary pycnometer⁸. From the measured densities d , the molar volumes were calculated using the relation,

$$V_m = (X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2) / d$$

where X_1 , X_2 , M_1 and M_2 are the mole fractions and molecular weights of solvent and solute respectively. The plot of V_m against X_2 is linear in accordance with the equation⁸,

$$V_m = V_1^0 + (\bar{V}_2 - V_1^0) X_2 \quad \dots (7)$$

With V_1^0 for the pure solvent known, it is now easy to determine \bar{V}_2 from the slope of the plot of V_m against X_2 .

The relative viscosities of the solutions were measured in an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer having viscometer constants, $A = 2.7321 \times 10^{-2}$ stokes/sec and $B = 1.3378 \times 10^{-2}$ stokes-sec. Kinetic energy correction was however negligible and the relative viscosity was determined from the relation, $\eta_{rel} = \frac{d_1 t_1}{d_0 t_0}$, where d_0 , t_0 and d_1 , t_1 are density and time of flow of pure solvent and solution respectively. Flow times were measured with a stopwatch reading upto $\frac{1}{10}$ th of a second. All measurements of density and of flow times were done in a thermostated bath at $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 gives the experimental results of viscosity measurements of solutions of the hydrocarbons

in various solvents. The plot of η_{rel} vs X_2 , mole fraction of solute is linear for all the solutes in these solvents. Figure 1 is a typical linear plot of η_{rel} vs X_2 of fluorene in the solvents in the low concentration range used in the present investigation. The experimental values of the slope, S_0 of the η_{rel} vs X_2 plot are also given in Table 4. The plots of V_m vs mole fraction of all the solutes, X_2 in these solvents

Fig. 1. Plot of η_{rel} vs mole fraction, X_2 of Fluorene in several solvents

Δ - *p*-xylene ; Left hand Y axis and lower X axis
 \circ - toluene ; Left hand Y axis and upper X axis
 \bullet - mesitylene ; Right hand Y axis and upper X axis
 \square - *o*-xylene ; Left hand Y axis and upper X axis

TABLE 1—RELATIVE VISCOSITIES OF HYDROCARBONS IN SOLVENTS AT $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$

Solvent	Mole fraction of solute X_2	η_{rel}	Solvent	Mole fraction of solute X_2	η_{rel}
Naphthalene					
<i>o</i> -xylene	0.0225	1.0257	<i>m</i> -xylene	0.0489	1.0510
	0.0440	1.0461		0.0643	1.0774
	0.0644	1.0657		0.0888	1.1129
	0.0843	1.0967		0.1085	1.1300
<i>p</i> -xylene	0.0225	1.0236	toluene	0.0070	1.0087
	0.0464	1.0503		0.0128	1.0150
	0.0681	1.0766		0.0613	1.0779
	0.0888	1.1052			
<i>n</i> -heptane	0.0679	1.0672			
	0.1028	1.1101			
	0.1273	1.1399			
2 : 3-dimethylnaphthalene					
<i>o</i> -xylene	0.0185	1.0243	<i>m</i> -xylene	0.0187	1.0300
	0.0329	1.0447		0.0330	1.0530
	0.0466	1.0650		0.0503	1.0777
	0.0603	1.0858		0.0669	1.1049
<i>p</i> -xylene	0.0190	1.0283	mesitylene	0.0210	1.0315
	0.0446	1.0638		0.0410	1.0606
	0.0569	1.0834		0.0532	1.0829
	0.0741	1.1067		0.0715	1.1079

(Table 1 Contd.)

Solvent	Mole fraction of solute X_2	η_{rel}	Solvent	Mole fraction of solute X_2	η_{rel}
2 : 6-dimethylnaphthalene					
o-xylene	0.0185	1.0257	m-xylene	0.0185	1.0315
	0.0364	1.0491		0.0364	1.0593
	0.0567	1.0766		0.0567	1.0838
	0.0744	1.1007		0.0784	1.1186
	0.0928	1.1263			
p-xylene	0.0196	1.0258	mesitylene	0.0209	1.0242
	0.0385	1.0516		0.0433	1.0509
	0.0600	1.0824		0.0556	1.0682
	0.0784	1.1034		0.0674	1.0872
	0.0961	1.1345			
toluene	0.0162	1.0260			
	0.0317	1.0511			
	0.0468	1.0768			
	0.0603	1.1004			
	0.0757	1.1266			
o-terphenyl					
o-xylene	0.0064	1.0189	m-xylene	0.0064	1.0255
	0.0128	1.0497		0.0127	1.0486
	0.0211	1.0788		0.0189	1.0751
	0.0250	1.0955		0.0250	1.0975
p-xylene	0.0064	1.0233	mesitylene	0.0072	1.0201
	0.0134	1.0483		0.0143	1.0495
	0.0199	1.0737		0.0213	1.0689
	0.0264	1.1002		0.0282	1.1010
	0.0341	1.1292		0.0396	1.1158
Durene					
m-xylene	0.0322	1.0191	p-xylene	0.0399	1.0188
	0.0587	1.0353		0.0811	1.0497
	0.0873	1.0510		0.1114	1.0629
	0.1203	1.0701		0.1467	1.0743
toluene	0.0176	1.0092	n-heptane	0.0335	1.0271
	0.0348	1.0183		0.0650	1.0538
	0.0673	1.0406		0.1105	1.0921
Hexamethylbenzene					
o-xylene	0.0184	1.0258	m-xylene	0.0179	1.0302
	0.0283	1.0428		0.0319	1.0545
	0.0426	1.0657		0.0489	1.0751
	0.0551	1.0856		0.0647	1.1003
mesitylene	0.0203	1.0277			
	0.0359	1.0466			
	0.0509	1.0719			
	0.0666	1.0965			
Fluoranthene					
o-xylene	0.0072	1.0223	p-xylene	0.0144	1.0401
	0.0144	1.0444		0.0214	1.0611
	0.0283	1.0887		0.0283	1.0821
	0.0419	1.1389		0.0391	1.1207
	0.0551	1.1780		0.0525	1.1566
mesitylene	0.0082	1.0226	toluene	0.0125	1.0422
	0.0162	1.0450		0.0230	1.0755
	0.0257	1.0721		0.0318	1.1063
	0.0350	1.1005		0.0414	1.1409
	0.0472	1.1386		0.0500	1.1747
Fluorene					
o-xylene	0.0088	1.0160	p-xylene	0.0177	1.0338
	0.0175	1.0336		0.0327	1.0637
	0.0276	1.0532		0.0502	1.0985
	0.0408	1.0807		0.0666	1.1349
mesitylene	0.0099	1.0196	toluene	0.0151	1.0341
	0.0203	1.0369		0.0298	1.0695
	0.0311	1.0561		0.0441	1.1047
	0.0460	1.0852		0.0581	1.1380
	0.0604	1.1132		0.0717	1.1775

Fig. 2. Plot of V_m vs mole fraction, X_2 of o-terphenyl in several solvents. \circ -p-xylene, Δ -o-xylene and \square -mesitylene; Left hand Y axis \bullet -m-xylene, Right hand Y axis

are linear and a typical plot is shown in Fig. 2. The values of \bar{V}_2 as determined from the slope are given in Table 2 together with the values of V_1^0 for the pure solvents.

To obtain the value of A in expression (6) for solvents, we employ the relation⁸,

$$A = \frac{\Delta E_1^{\ddagger}}{\Delta G^*_{vis}} = \frac{\Delta H_1^{\ddagger} - RT}{\Delta G^*_{vis}}$$

From the published vapour pressure¹ of the solvents, we evaluated ΔH_1^{\ddagger} , enthalpy of vaporisation of solvents from the linear plot of log (vapour pressure) vs $1/T$. With the help of Eyring equation for viscosity of pure solvent, η ,

$$\eta = \frac{Nh}{\bar{V}_1^0} \exp(\Delta G^*_{vis}/RT) \quad \dots (8)$$

it is possible to obtain the value of ΔG^*_{vis} , free activation energy of viscous flow for a solvent with known viscosity at T°K. In eq. (8) R, N and h are molar gas constant, Avogadro's number and Planck's constant respectively. The viscosities of the solvents at 35° were used for evaluating ΔG^*_{vis} given in Table 3. With the values of ΔE_1^{\ddagger} and ΔG^*_{vis} thus determined, we calculated the value of A for the solvents and these are given in Table 3. The values of the solubility parameter δ_1 for

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $\bar{V}_2, \bar{V}_1^0, \delta_1$ AND δ_2 AT $35 \pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$

Solvent	Naphthalene		Durene		2 : 3-dimethylnaphthalene		2 : 6-dimethylnaphthalene		Hexamethylbenzene	
	$\bar{V}_2(\text{cc mole}^{-1})$	δ_2	$\bar{V}_2(\text{cc mole}^{-1})$	δ_2						
<i>o</i> -xylene	124.89	9.70	—	—	155.46	8.95	159.18	8.79	175.62	8.497
<i>m</i> -xylene	124.49	9.73	154.10	8.40	155.05	8.93	157.69	8.80	175.40	8.47
<i>p</i> -xylene	125.03	9.60	152.72	8.38	156.01	8.82	158.42	8.69	—	—
mesitylene	—	—	—	—	156.24	8.92	158.18	8.76	175.22	8.40
<i>n</i> -heptane	124.64	9.00	153.41	7.89	—	—	—	—	—	—
toluene	124.85	9.17	154.00	7.86	—	—	158.07	8.44	—	—
Mean :		9.44 ± 0.33		8.13 ± 0.30		8.90 ± 0.06		8.696 ± 0.15		8.45 ± 0.05

Solvent	<i>o</i> -terphenyl		Fluoranthene		Fluorene		Solvents	
	$\bar{V}_2(\text{cc mole}^{-1})$	δ_2	$\bar{V}_2(\text{cc mole}^{-1})$	δ_2	$\bar{V}_2(\text{cc mole}^{-1})$	δ_2	$\bar{V}_1^0(\text{cc mole}^{-1})$	δ_1
<i>o</i> -xylene	215.88	8.83	172.12	9.58	154.20	9.33	122.18	8.96
<i>m</i> -xylene	213.36	8.79	—	—	—	—	124.49	8.75
<i>p</i> -xylene	213.60	8.76	171.398	9.32	152.95	9.26	125.03	8.70
mesitylene	213.19	8.26	171.25	9.04	153.06	9.15	140.96	8.76
<i>n</i> -heptane	—	—	—	—	—	—	149.03	7.40
toluene	—	—	172.92	9.04	152.64	9.04	107.93	8.86
Mean :		8.66 ± 0.27		9.24 ± 0.26		9.19 ± 0.13		

solvents at 25° are already available in literature⁷. Assuming that ΔE_1^* is independent of temperature,

 TABLE 3—VALUES OF ΔG_{vis}^* , ΔE_1^V AND A FOR PURE SOLVENTS AT $35 \pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$

Solvents	ΔH_1^V (cal mole ⁻¹)	$\Delta E_1^V = \Delta H_1^V - RT$ (cal mole ⁻¹)	ΔG_{vis}^* (cal mole ⁻¹)	A
<i>o</i> -xylene	10284	9672	3249	2.977
<i>m</i> -xylene	9776	9164	3112	2.945
<i>p</i> -xylene	9908	9296	3135	2.965
mesitylene	6358	5746	3267	1.759
<i>n</i> -heptane	8494	7882	2980	2.645
toluene	8764	8152	2991	2.725

the value of δ_1 at 35° was determined by multiplying its value at 25° with the ratio of partial molal volumes of the solvent at these two temperatures. The values of δ_1 at 35° are given in Table 2. We can now determine the solubility parameter of a solute hydrocarbon, if we substitute in eq. (4) the values of $\delta_1, \bar{V}_1^0, \bar{V}_2, A$ and the experimental S_o which are given in Tables 2, 3 and 4 respectively. We have thus determined δ_2 for the various solutes and these are given in Table 2 along with the mean over various solvents. We now calculate the viscosity function, $F = \bar{V}_2 \left(\frac{2\delta_2}{\delta_1} - 1 \right)$ using the mean values of δ_2 . The values of \bar{V}_2 and δ_1 necessary for the calculation are taken from Table 2. We observe

 TABLE 4—VALUES OF S_o AND F FOR SOLUTES IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Solvents	Hexamethyl-							
	<i>o</i> -terphenyl	Fluoranthene	Fluorene	benzene	2 : 3 DMN†	2 : 6 DMN†	Naphthalene	Durene
<i>o</i> -xylene S_o (Expt)	3.8461	3.240†	1.9624	1.5438	1.4461	1.3516	1.0303	—
<i>o</i> -xylene F	190.15	183.07	162.12	155.63	153.55	149.94	134.36	—
<i>m</i> -xylene S_o (Expt)	3.8559	—	—	1.6842	1.5614	1.4921	1.1935	0.6038
<i>m</i> -xylene F	197.56	—	—	163.37	160.54	155.89	140.13	128.74
<i>p</i> -xylene S_o (Expt)	3.8257	2.9394	1.9697	—	1.4621	1.3647	1.0806	0.6818
<i>p</i> -xylene F	200.15	192.87	170.18	—	163.36	158.42	142.27	129.20
<i>n</i> -heptane S_o (Expt)	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.0000	0.8293
<i>n</i> -heptane F	—	—	—	—	—	—	188.64	179.53
toluene S_o (Expt)	—	3.3958	2.4024	—	—	1.6537	1.2162	0.5283
toluene F	—	187.95	164.01	—	—	152.36	137.25	125.15
mesitylene S_o (Expt)	3.40	2.9198	1.8276	1.4067*	1.50*	1.2192	—	—
mesitylene F	196.93	190.23	168.08	162.83	161.41	156.01	—	—

† DMN : Dimethylnaphthalene.

* It is noted that for solutes hexamethylbenzene and 2 : 3-dimethylnaphthalene the order of S_o is reversed in mesitylene.

that the viscosity function is always positive as it should be. Further, F decreases in the same order as experimental (mean) S_o shown in Table 4 for the various solutes in the given solvents. Excepting for the solvent mesitylene, it is seen that the computed values of F decrease in the same order as the observed values of S_o , as it should. It is evident that the prediction that larger the value of the viscosity function, F , the greater will be the slope, S_o of the plot of η_{rel} vs X_2 is generally fulfilled by the above experimental results. It is true that we should have made an independent determination of δ_2 for evaluating the viscosity function, F . In absence of any independent estimate of δ_2 , we have taken values of δ_2 averaged over several solvents. In addition to the fact that Irving and Smith equation gives a new method for estimating solubility parameters, it is all the more important because it brings out clearly that it is the solubility parameters and partial molar volumes of

solvent and solute that determine in a large measure the viscosity behaviour of non-electrolyte solutions.

References

1. J. R. PARTINGTON, *An Adv. Treatise on Physical Chemistry* (Longmans), 1951, **2**, 70, 251.
2. R. H. STOKES and R. MILLS, *Viscosity of Electrolytes and Related Properties*, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1965.
3. H. IRVING and J. S. SMITH, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1873.
4. H. IRVING and J. S. SMITH, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 1212.
5. S. GLASSTONE., K. J. LAIDLER and H. EYRING, *The Theory of Rate Processes* (New York: McGraw Hill), 1941, 480.
6. G. SCATCHARD, *Chem. Rev.*, 1931, **8**, 321.
7. J. H. HILDEBRAND and R. L. SCOTT, *The Solubility of Nonelectrolytes* (Dover Publications, Inc. New York), Third Edition, 1950.
8. A. WEISSBERGER, *Physical Methods of Organic Chemistry* (Interscience Publishers, Inc, New York), **1**, 148.